

TAX Justice and Non-Financial Performance of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises in Ogun State West Senatorial District

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Abstract

In Nigeria Small and Medium Enterprises are faced with problem of inadequate supply of infrastructural facilities by government despite the fact that they pay numerous types of taxes. This study examined the effect of tax justice on non-financial performance of SMEs in Ogun West Senatorial District. The population of the study comprises 658 Enterprises in 5 local government areas in Ogun West Senatorial District. A sample size of 300 enterprises were selected using proportional sampling procedure. The data were collected through questionnaire analyzed using descriptive statistics and multiple regression analysis. The study's findings indicated that tax justice has significant effect on workers welfare ($p < 0.05$); and employment generation ($p < 0.05$). The study concluded that tax justice has significant effect on non-financial performance ($p < 0.05$) and recommended that Ogun state government should provide necessary infrastructural facilities to assist the SMEs in their business operations.

Keywords: Tax justice; Non-financial performance; Small and medium scale enterprises (SMEs); Employment generation and workers welfare.

Introduction

Tax justice has been looked at from different perspectives. In India and Kenya tax justice campaign occurred from protests against colonial rule, also from Ghana and Philippines, reactions emanating from structural adjustment programme's unjustified tax charge. In Europe and United States, issue of tax justice are directed towards tax related and hidden financial resources as the major obstacle that resulted in loss of revenues in developing countries. Abdel-Karim (2018) emphasized that the issues of Tax justice remained very crucial in all nations, however, Some developing nations and the Arab countries and has other conditions which include justified important public services financial expenditure, infrastructural, economic and social development sustainability; thereby looking for justified and fair tax burden distribution, high level of tax and financial discipline with the aid of public oversight monitoring transparency in the making of fiscal and tax policy.

The small and medium scale has important role to play in employment generation and economic development that are common to human existence. Therefore, there is an ever increasing agitation for more investments in small and medium scale enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria. This is evident from the recently enacted Finance Act 2020 which exempted small businesses with annual turnover that are lesser than or equal to N25 million from the payment of companies income tax, while medium scale enterprises with turnover that are above N25 million but not more than N100 million are to be taxed at the rate of 15% and larger firms with turnover greater than N100 million at 30%. Also the Company and Allied Matters Act 2020 (CAMA 2020) which follows the trend in Finance Act 2020.

Tax justice has been a general concept developed by the human rights movements, academics and civil society in order to enable stakeholders to articulate their discovery as acceptable in a tax system in a government that is accountable to the people. It is basically established with the rational view that funds generated from taxation is to provide public goods. That is funds taken from the populace should be given back to society according to their needs (roads, electricity, pipe borne water, social and development space for the younger ones to develop and handle and handle the situation to maturity. Olabisi, Afolabi, Olagunju and Madariola (2020) emphasized that the major source of revenue for government to execute her civic obligations to the populace comes from tax income.

Tax Justice Network (2009) emphasized that the most crucial elements should involve respect for social welfare and human rights requirements by allowing tax as an appendage of right-based governance system by giving the chance for the voices of the less privileged alongside that of powerful people with special interest.

Performance of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) has been of great concern to various investors in Nigeria because of multiplicity of taxes and lack of adequate provision of infrastructural facilities to justify the huge tax collection by various governments at the three levels of governance, that is Federal, State and Local Governments. Both financial and non-financial performance yardsticks can be used to analyse the performance of SMEs.

There are many studies conducted in the arena of tax justice both from developed and developing countries but not many examined it in relation to non-financial performance of SMEs in Ogun State West Senatorial District. Nasser (2018) focused on Tax Justice and sustainable development in the Arab Region with tax system's lessons from four Countries, Palestine, Egypt, Jordan and Lebanon. Akintoye and Dada (2016) examined the influence of tax justice and economic growth and development in African Sub-Saharan environment with evidence from Nigeria. Ebere, Eunice, and Chimaobi (2016) evaluate the effect of multiple taxation on investment in Small and Medium Enterprises in Enugu State Nigeria. This study is motivated as a result of the available gap existing from the past studies stemming from the knowledge that few studies were done in the area of tax justice in developing countries. Therefore, this study focused on reducing the gap to the lowest level.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study is to examine the effect of tax justice on non-financial performance of small and medium scale enterprises in Ogun West Senatorial District.

The specific objectives are to:

- i. Examine the influence of tax justice on workers welfare of SMEs in Ogun West Senatorial District
- ii. Evaluate the effect of tax justice on employment generation of SMEs in Ogun West Senatorial District.

Research Questions

The following research questions were developed to guide the researcher in achieving its objectives.

- i. To what extent does tax justice affect workers welfare of SMEs in Ogun West Senatorial District?
- ii. What effect does tax justice has on employment generation of SMEs in Ogun West Senatorial District?

Research Hypotheses

In order to achieve the stated objectives, the following hypotheses were formulated.

H_{01} : Tax justice has no significant effect on workers welfare of SMEs in Ogun West Senatorial District

H_{02} : Tax justice has no significant effect on employment generation of SMEs in Ogun West Senatorial District.

Literature Review

Conceptual Review

Tax Justice

Tax justice can be viewed from different perspective ranging from equity in tax systems among individual taxpayers to the side of government in using the funds collected from taxes justifiably and providing better life and good socio-economic growth for the tax payers, citizens, and residents within its geo-political environment. Nasser (2018) while referring to protests in Jordan in 2018 emphasized that tax systems equity has significant influence on tax justice in the Arab environment and that majority of the residents accept that they are faced with unfair burden of tax charges emanating from direct taxes imposed on them as they would have preferred the effective taxation of wealth. They also complain on inadequacy of employment, public services and infrastructural facilities for the citizens. Lethbridge (2016) opined that in Nigeria, there is a high level of personal income tax evasion coupled with low rate of personal taxation and tax evasion is a common phenomenon in many Africa countries which is affecting government revenues and the supply of public services. Adebisi and Gbegi (2013) found that in order to reduce tax evasion by individual taxpayers, it is necessary to spend sufficient government revenue on public goods and services with adequate investment in tax collection services and staff.

Oyedokun (2016) opined that tax justice has become an increasingly major issue of political debate in many developed and emerging countries around the world. It became more significant particularly following the cardiac arrest of the global financial system in 2008 and the subsequent worldwide slump in trade and production.

According to FIRS (2018), Tax justice is a fair system for taxing which centered on the need to support public services, reduce the national deficit, prevent unfair corporate tax practices, confront tax avoidance and evasion as well as achieving tax transparency. FIRS

(2018) further explained the importance of tax justice which result from the need for multinational corporation, financiers and wealthy/rich personality to pay their fair share of tax; the need for concern on the situation where national and international system that support tax evasion, tax avoidance and tax havens; the requirement for fair, progressive, sufficient and transparent resourced tax administration; also the need for all citizens and residents to receive their fair share of social protection and public services.

Non-Financial Performance

Performance can be seen from two perspectives, that is financial and non-financial performance. Financial performance measures generally focus on annual financial statements and reports which is short-term performance measures using accounting yardsticks. Where managers uses these measures neglecting strategic long term goals, it can result in counter-productive behaviour. Non-financial performance on the other hand provides organizations with information which can help in making decisions for the future activities which are useful for planning purposes (Udechukwu, 2016).

Non-Financial Performance indicators are progressive in relation to satisfying the customers beyond their expectations and achieving a competitive advantage in the industry because they are very important in meeting profitability targets and other strategic long-term objectives (Afuberoh & Okoye, 2016). DuRietz and Henrekson (2018) emphasized that by replacing financial performance with non-financial data focusing on strategic plan implementation and strategic performance will help businesses to provide the managers with objectives and incentives to pursue long-term strategies as it is capable of capturing critical non-financial and industry-related performance indices.

According to Akintoye and Tashie (2015) non-Financial Performance measures provide general view of a business' operations and dynamic information. It allow businesses to facilitate their evaluation of performance using both qualitative and quantitative indicators which will assist monitoring of operational activities continuously leading to the discovery of weaknesses and enable chance for improvements. This will enable a business to be in control of its external and internal environment which allow for the adoption of better strategies for improving its management activities and performance (Rahn, 2016).

Conceptual Model

Figure 1: Operationalization of Variables Model Explaining Tax Justice and Non-Financial Performance (Author's Conceptual Model)

Theoretical Framework

The study was premised on Benefit (Quid Pro Quo) Theory and Laffer curve Theory. Benefit theory was developed by Erick Lindal while Arthur Laffer propounded the Laffer Curve theory. The benefit theory is relevant because it agreed that taxes should be apportioned to individual according to the benefits, they received from government

expenditure and services even though it negate basis upon which tax operates but taxpayers must be given services that will better their lives. The Laffer curve theory positively correlated with the attitude and behaviour of an average taxpayer which could either be a human being or a business concern. It emphasized that lower tax rates boost economic growth. Omokhuale (2016) and Afuberoh and Okoye (2016), opined that the effect of this theory is that increasing tax rate beyond a certain point will result in counter-productive because raising further raising tax rates will lead to diminishing returns of tax revenue. This theory is relevant and applicable to the current Nigerian situation where eligible taxpayers avoid payment of taxes due to the high tax rate. The relevancy of these theories formed the pivot upon which this research work rotates.

Empirical Review

Setyorini and Susilowati (2018) examined analysis of implementation of SMEs Tax Enforcement with specific focus on the effects of tax justice dimensions, understanding of tax accounting on SME's tax compliance. Quantitative deductive research design was adopted with the population being SMEs registered in Department of Cooperatives, Trade and Industry in Banyumas, Purbalinga and Cilacap. Convenience sampling was used for the collection of data using questionnaire and semi-structured interviews covering 115 SMEs. The study showed that the SMEs tax compliance is affected by understanding on tax justice and tax accounting. The work also revealed that the majority of SMEs do not understand tax accounting hence most respondents still doubt the reality of tax justice.

Oyedokun, Akintoye and Salawu (2018) examined the effect of tax justice on federally collected tax revenue in Nigeria. A vector autoregressive approach. The study analyze the strength and relevance of tax justice in improving federally collected tax revenue in Nigeria. The study adopted ex-post facto research design using secondary data gathered from Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS), Federal Ministry of Finance, Accountant general of the Federation, Central bank of Nigeria (CBN), and Nigeria Bureau of Statistics (NBS) (2016 Statistical Bulletin). The population of the study involves all the figures of tax revenue, Gross Domestic Product and Government Expenditure per sector as reported within the period of 17 years (2000 - 2016). It indicated that tax justice will promote tax compliance and in turn improve tax revenue collected in Nigeria by the Federal Government. The study concluded that promoting tax justice will assist the increase of tax revenue in Nigeria.

Bismark, Joy and Evans (2016) assessed tax policy, SMEs compliance perception and growth relationship in Ghana. The findings showed that majority of the respondents

accept that tax policies have adverse effect on SMEs compliance, growth and perception in Nigeria. Ebere, Eunice, and Chimaobi, (2016), examined the effect of multiple taxation on investment in small and medium enterprises. The study found that multiple taxation affect SMEs investment negatively and that SMEs investment has significant relationship with the ability to pay tax. Ocheni, and Gemade (2015), evaluated effect of multiple taxation on SMEs survival and found that multiple taxation has negative effect on SMEs' survival. The study also discovered that the relationship between SMEs' size and its ability to pay taxes is significant.

Methods

Procedure

The design adopted for this study is a descriptive survey research design. All information that were required for the success of this research were provided using primary data through questionnaire and responses from the participants. The questionnaire was administered in December, 2019 and the literature was updated in 2020/2021. The data gathering instrument employed for this study was a structured questionnaire using 5-point Likert scale. The population of the study comprises of all SMEs (registered and unregistered) gathered through visits by the researcher to the five (5) Local government councils and Ogun State Chamber of Commerce under Ogun West Senatorial District.

The SMEs covered include businessmen and women of small and medium size businesses, Artisans, Technicians, Professionals, Market men and Women Trader, Wholesalers, Retailers, Hotel, Transportation and manufacturers of local products. The total population was 658 out of which 300 sample sizes were selected. The sampling technique adopted was proportional sampling method to allocate the 300 sampling size among the five (5) Local Government councils as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Population and Sample size analysis

S/N	LOCAL GOVT	TOTAL POPULATION (SMEs)	SAMPLE SIZE	QUESTIONAIRES RETURNED
1.	Yewa South	146	67	64
2.	Yewa North	47	21	21

3.	Ado- Odo/Ota	308	140	136
4.	Ipokia	125	57	56
5.	Imeko	32	15	15
	Total	658	300	292

Source: Researcher's Field survey, 2023

Population

The population of the study comprises of all registered and unregistered SMEs in the five (5) local government councils under Ogun West Senatorial District: They are:

Table 2: Population Source of Registered SMEs

SN	Detail	SMEs Number
i.	Yewa South Local Government	4
ii.	Yewa North Local Government	8
iii.	Ado-Odo/Ota Local Government	65
iv.	Ipokia Local Government	7
v.	Imeko-Afon Local Government	3
	Total	87

Source: Ogun State Chamber of Commerce, 2023

The figure of the registered SMEs was eighty-seven (87) while the unregistered SMEs which were visited by the researcher was 213 out of 566. The breakdown of the population of unregistered SMEs in the 5 local government areas are given below:

Table 3: Population Source of Unregistered SMEs

SN	Detail	SMEs Number
i.	Yewa South Local Government	142
ii.	Yewa North Local Government	39
iii.	Ado-Odo/Ota Local Government	243
iv.	Ipokia Local Government	118
v.	Imeko-Afon Local Government	24
	Total	566

Source: Researcher’s Field Survey, 2023

Sample Size and Sampling Technique

There are five (5) local government under Ogun West Senatorial District, which form the population for this study, After using proportional sampling procedure for the sample size, judgmental sampling technique was used to determine choice of SMEs from each of the five (5) Local Governments with consideration for the number of populations from each Local Government because of uneven spread and characteristics of the entire population . The total sample size is 300 consisting of 87 Registered SMEs and 213 Unregistered SMEs.

Model Specification

In order to obtain statistical evidence for the study and for the control of possible confounding effect of observable characteristics, this econometric model using cross sectional analysis is estimated:

$$Y = f(x)$$

Where:

Y = Non-financial Performance (NFP) representing Dependent Variable

Y1 = Workers Welfare (WW)

Y2 = Employment Generation (EG)

X = Tax Justice (TJ) representing Independent Variable

X1 = Redistribution of Income (RI)

X2 = Tax Transparency (TT)

X3 = Tax Equity and Equality (TEE)

Functional Model

Model 1

$$WW = \beta_0 + \beta_1 RI; + \beta_2 TT; + \beta_3 TEE + \varepsilon t$$

Model 2

$$EG = \beta_0 + \beta_1 RI; + \beta_2 TT; + \beta_3 TEE + \varepsilon t$$

Overall Model

$$NFP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 RI; + \beta_2 TT; + \beta_3 TEE + \varepsilon t$$

Where:

$$NFP = (\underline{EG} + WW)$$

Validity and Reliability Test

The validity of the research instrument was achieved using content validity. The reliability test for this research was achieved using Cronbach Alpha's test is presented in the Table 3.1

Table 4: Summary of the Reliability Test

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	No of items
Tax Justice	0.76	4
Workers Welfare	0.75	5
Employment Generation	0.82	5

Source: Researcher's Field Survey, 2023

The Table 4 shows the reliability of the various variables as contained in the questionnaire used for the survey research. Cronbach's alpha values are 0.76 for tax justice, 0.75 for workers welfare, 0.82 for employment generation. The high reliability value is an indication that the questionnaire is highly reliable to obtain information concerning the variables under-study.

Data Analysis Method

The analysis adopted both descriptive and inferential statistical methods. Analysis was done using linearity, normality, homoscedasticity, and cross sectional analysis under econometric model. The reason is that it is a Descriptive survey analysis with the use of a questionnaire. The R2 value and the Beta coefficient as well as its significance was analyzed and examined on all of the dimensions relationships. Multiple regression analysis was carried out using E-view statistical package.

A priori Expectation and Decision Criteria

The decision criterion for the rejection or acceptance of the hypotheses for this study was set at 5% level of significance. The researcher expects a positive significant effect of the independent variable over dependent variables.

Ethical Consideration

Ethics of research were observed in the course of carrying out this research. All works of other scholars referenced in the research were properly cited to avoid plagiarism. Similarly, the participants in the research, who were served copies of questionnaire, were informed about the purpose of the information sought from them.

Results

The statistical tools used for the testing of the research instrument were descriptive statistics such as frequency distribution and percentages and regression analysis with the aid of e-view 10. A total of 300 questionnaires were distributed in which 292 questionnaires were fully filled and returned. The remaining eight (8) not returned was due to the nonchalant attitude of the eight (8) respondents. The returned questionnaires were suitable for further analysis and the return rate was 97%. Both Fixed and random effects were tested, after which Hausman test was performed and gave probability of 0.0000 which is significant at 5% hence fixed effect is appropriate for the analysis.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1:

H_01 : Tax Justice does not have significant effect on workers welfare.

Table 5: Regression analysis of the effect of tax justice on workers welfare

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
RI	-0.567290	0.100227	-5.660025	0.0000
TT	1.145078	0.263577	4.344387	0.0000
TEE	0.900654	0.169725	5.306554	0.0000
C	9.807600	0.984527	9.961742	0.0000
R-squared	0.639701	Mean dependent var		16.69863
Adjusted R-squared	0.628826	S.D. dependent var		1.989214
S.E. of regression	1.769366	Akaike info criterion		3.996095
Sum squared resid	898.4983	Schwarz criterion		4.059053

Log likelihood	-578.4298	Hannan-Quinn criter.	4.021313
F-statistic	20.20193	Durbin-Watson stat	1.579176
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000		

Source: Researcher's computation, 2023

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Log likelihood	-578.4298	Hannan-Quinn criter.		4.021313
F-statistic	20.20193	Durbin-Watson stat		1.579176
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Source: Researcher's computation, 2023

Interpretation of Result

From the result in Table 5, the constant value of 9.807600 suggest that a unit increase in tax justice will result in 980.76 increase in Workers welfare (WW). From the table, the coefficient value of redistribution of income (RI) is -0.567290 and the t-statistics is -5.660025 which indicates a negative significance on the dependent variable (Workers welfare [WW]) but is statistically significant at 0.0000. Similarly, the coefficient value of tax transparency standing at 1.145078 and the t-statistics value of 4.344387 indicates that tax transparency has positive effect on the dependent variable and is statistically significant at 0.0000. Tax Equity and Equality (TEE) has a positive co-efficient value of 0.900654 and t-statistics value of 5.306554 which means it has a positive effect on the dependent variable Workers welfare (WW) and is statistically significant at 0.0000. The respective standard errors for the independent variables are; 0.100227, 0.263577 and 0.169725. The p-values are less than 0.05 significant level, which is an indication that all the independent variables are statistically significant. Also, the R-squared value indicates that about 63.9% variations in workers welfare could be attributed to the joint effects of the independent variables. In addition, the f-statistics value is given as 20.2019 with p-value (0.0000). This result suggests that the model is significant and hence the alternative hypothesis is accepted because the p-value is less than the significant value of 5%.

The alternative hypothesis is therefore accepted, and we concluded that tax justice has a significant effect on workers welfare.

Hypothesis 2:

H_02 : Tax Justice does not have significant effect on employment generation.

Table 6: Regression analysis of the effect of tax justice on employment generation

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
RI	0.068745	0.081914	0.839228	0.4020
TT	0.745184	0.215017	3.465700	0.0006
TEE	-0.060372	0.138590	-0.435616	0.6634
C	10.93831	0.806197	13.56779	0.0000

R-squared	0.596256	Mean dependent var	13.98966
Adjusted R-squared	0.583572	S.D. dependent var	1.507730
S.E. of regression	1.443354	Akaike info criterion	3.588907
Sum squared resid	593.7319	Schwarz criterion	3.652181
Log likelihood	-515.3915	Hannan-Quinn criter.	3.614257
F-statistic	7.588682	Durbin-Watson stat	2.442268
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000008		

Source: Researcher's computation, 2023

Interpretation of Result

From the result in Table 6, the constant value 10.93831 suggest that a unit increase in tax justice will result in 109.38 increase in employment generation (EG). From the table, the coefficient value of redistribution of income (RI) is 0.068745 and the t-statistics is 0.839228 which indicates a positive significance on the dependent variable (Physical employment generation [EG]) but is statistically insignificant at 0.4020. Similarly, the coefficient value of tax transparency standing at 0.745184 and the t-statistics value of 3.465700 indicates that tax transparency has a positive effect on the dependent variable and is statistically significant at 0.0006. Tax Equity and Equality (TEE) has a negative co-efficient value of -0.060372 and t-statistics value of 0.435616 which means it has a negative effect on the dependent variable employment generation (EG) and is statistically insignificant at 0.6634. The respective standard errors for the independent variables are; 0.081914, 0.215017 and 0.138590. Only the p-value of tax transparency (TT) is statistically significant at 5% while redistribution of income (RI) and tax equity and equality (TEE) are statistically insignificant with the values 0.4020 and 0.6634 respectively.

However, the joint effects of independent variables resulted in F-value given as 7.588682 with p-value (0.000008) which is less than the acceptable level of significance. This result suggests that the model is significant and hence the alternative hypothesis is accepted because the p-value < 0.05 significant value. The alternative hypothesis is therefore accepted, and we conclude that, Tax justice has significant effect on employment generation.

Hypothesis 3: For overall result

H_0 : Tax Justice does not have significant effect on non-financial performance of SMEs.

Table 7: Regression analysis of the effect of tax justice on non -financial performance

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
RI	-0.701675	0.257038	-2.729848	0.0067
TT	-2.767747	0.673771	-4.107843	0.0001
TEE	-1.109800	0.434886	-2.551934	0.0112
C	49.87027	2.542049	19.61814	0.0000
R-squared	0.513838	Mean dependent var		63.78819
Adjusted R-squared	0.501312	S.D. dependent var		4.770730
S.E. of regression	4.522610	Akaike info criterion		5.873264
Sum squared resid	5788.484	Schwarz criterion		5.936858
Log likelihood	-840.7501	Hannan-Quinn criter.		5.898749
F-statistic	9.088639	Durbin-Watson stat		1.510356
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000001			

Source: Researcher's computation, 2023

Interpretation of Result

From the result in Table 7, the constant value 49.87027 suggest that a unit increase in tax justice will result in 498.70 increase in non-financial performance (NFP). From the table, the coefficient value of redistribution of income (RI) is -0.701675 and the t-statistics is -2.729848 which indicates a negative significance on the dependent variable (Non-financial

performance [NFP]) but is statistically significant at 0.0067. Similarly, the coefficient value of tax transparency standing at -2.7677 and the t-statistics value of -4.1078 indicates that Tax transparency has a negative effect on the dependent variable but is statistically significant at 0.0001. Tax Equity and Equality (TEE) has a negative co-efficient value of -1.1098 and t-statistics value of -2.5519 which means it has a negative effect on the dependent variable social responsibility (SR) but is statistically significant at 0.0112. The respective standard errors for the independent variables are; 0.257038, 0.673771 and 0.434886. The p-values are less than the significant value of 0.05, which is an indication that all of the independent variables are statistically significant.

Also, the R-squared value indicates that about 51.3% variation in non-financial performance of the SMEs could be attributed to the joint effects of the independent variables. In addition, the F-value is given as 9.0886 with p-value (0.0000). This result suggests that the model is significant and hence the alternative hypothesis is accepted because the p-value < 0.05 significant level. The alternative hypothesis is therefore accepted, and we conclude that tax justice have a significant effect on non-financial performance of SMEs.

Discussion of Findings

In Table 5 analysis, it was concluded that tax justice (redistribution of income, tax transparency, tax equity and equality) has significant effect on workers welfare. This finding is in agreement with the study of Naser (2018) that examined tax justice and employment justice found that tax incentive and low corporate tax rates through deliberate tax policies to resolve employment challenges stimulate more investment that lead to increase in employment level and improved workers' welfare. In contrast to the finding of this study when we look at workers welfare as part of social responsibility, Evans, Dongmei and Michael (2016) in their study of the SMEs business in Ghana assessed the influence of government and other institutional support on social responsibility and concluded that support by government and other institutions have direct and insignificant impact on SMEs performance. The result also showed that negative relationship exist among support by institution and social responsibility of SMEs in Ghana. From the analysis presented in Table 6, it was revealed that tax justice has a significant effect on employment generation. This finding is in collaboration with the study of Poulson & Kaplan (2008) which studied the effect of tax justice on employment generation in the United States within the framework of an endogenous growth model. They found a significant effect of marginal tax rate on employment generation. Also, Tomlin (2008) and Atawodi and Ojeka (2012), economists argued that the smaller companies resources

directed towards tax justice are resources that could otherwise be used for reinvestment and facilitating employment generation. Also, Saez (2004) evaluated effectiveness and efficiency of direct tax instrument and indirect tax in term of income redistribution assessed both in term of short run and long run. The study indicated that in the short run, indirect taxes are favoured as a tool for income redistribution in a situation where skills are exogenous and individual taxpayers are constraint from moving from job to job. The study concluded that it is more reasonable to say that in the long run, people pick their occupation in view of the relative after-tax benefits.

In Table 7, it was ascertained that tax justice has a significant effect on non-financial performance of SMEs. This finding has the same focus with the study of Owolabi and Okwu (2011), which examined the contribution of tax policy on non-financial performance of SMEs of Lagos State Economy from 2001 to 2005. The study regressed non-financial indicator (infrastructural, environmental management, youth and social welfare, education sector, agricultural, healthcare, and transportation) on SMEs in Lagos State during the study period. Their findings indicated that Tax justice contributed positively to the performance of SMEs in Lagos State economy during the period studied. Isaac (2015) examined the effects of government taxation policy on non-financial performance of SMEs firms in Kenya. The study adopted an exploratory research design. The research findings revealed that government tax policy has a direct significant influence on non-financial performance of SMEs in Kenya.

On the other hand, Atamodi and Ojeka (2012) examined expansion and sustenance as indices of SMEs non-financial performance to ascertain the relationship that exists between tax policies, and non-financial performance of SMEs and found that considerable negative relationship exists between tax and businesses' performance but make itself higher (in terms of assets, social welfare, and employment.). The research established that high tax rates are the SMEs basic problem. Afshari, Adabili, and Ali (2012) used sales personnel number, age, array of products as non-financial performance indices to analyze the influence of tax on SME's growth. It concluded that tax has a strong relationship with all the dimensions used to measure SMEs performance.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The overall result of the two hypotheses is that tax justice has significant effect on the non-financial performance of SMEs in the Ogun State West Senatorial District comprising five (5) Local Government Councils.

Based on the results and conclusions of the findings, it is recommended that the condition of infrastructural facilities in Ogun West Senatorial District, should be given important consideration in order to bring about improvement in the performance of SME sector in terms of service delivery. Given that the SMEs in Ogun West Senatorial District is a force to be recognized as they take part in the role of achieving economic development and national growth, therefore, there is need for the government to improve the state of infrastructure in order to improve tax justice so as to help in minimizing costs of production and prices of goods/service.

Government should provide basic infrastructures like good roads, pipe-borne water, efficient electricity, health care facilities among others to the benefit of SMEs investors and those that are resident in the area as this will aid and improve the quality of services rendered by SMEs investors.

To enhance or increase revenue base of SMEs, the government should charge lower rate of tax payable by SMEs investors. The reduction in tax rate would enable them to have funds for other activities that will enable acquisition of more assets, bringing growth to their business, yield more profit, increase employment level and Gross Domestic Product of the Country.

There is a rising need for the government to establish tax policy in the country that would encourage SMEs as friendly policy on tax that will encourage more people to venture into SMEs.

Contribution to Knowledge

This study empirically ascertained that tax justice has a significant influence on the non-financial performance of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs) in Ogun West Senatorial District in Nigeria. This will contribute to the body of existing knowledge by unfolding that tax justice has significant effect on workers welfare and employment generation in the study area. Similarly, the study advocates that the provision of infrastructures such as good roads, regular electricity supply within the senatorial district can enhance the non-financial performance of SMEs in the study area.

Suggestions for Further Research

The study focused on SMEs in Ogun West Senatorial District in the Country, and a significant proportion of the sample was from the five (5) local governments within the Senatorial district. This therefore limits the applicability of the findings to other SMEs in

other parts of the country. The study suggests that this study be scaled up to include more SMEs in Nigeria and not just within Ogun State West Senatorial District. Such a study would help increase the reliability of the findings as well as applicability to other SMEs outside the Ogun West Senatorial District. Tax justice is one of the major problems facing Nigeria Tax Revenue Authority. In many cases the government has lost a lot of revenue through this menace. Further studies can be done on this subject by replicating the study and using secondary data. Tax justice is very important for economic growth and development of a country. Nigeria economic growth is said to be growing steadily in the recent years. Does tax justice have any implication to it? This is what other researchers can determine.

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